

Integrated germplasm improvement

Altering associations between characters in rice through gamma radiation

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We studied the usefulness of gamma radiation in altering character association in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.).

Dry seeds of cultivar J112 were treated with gamma rays (^{60}Co) with 15, 25, and 35 Krad doses. We conducted variability studies in the M_2 and M_3 generations. The M_3 progenies were grown along with parental varieties in an experiment that was laid out in a randomized block design during the 1993-94 dry season. Of 30 random plants, correlation coefficients were calculated for plant height, panicles plant $^{-1}$, panicle length, panicle weight, grains panicle $^{-1}$, 1000-grain weight, and yield plant $^{-1}$.

The treatments with gamma rays increased the correlation between panicle length and yield plant $^{-1}$, panicle width, and grains panicle $^{-1}$, and between panicle weight and grains panicle $^{-1}$, and plant height and plant weight (see table). This increased correlation among traits can be used to increase the rate of selection response for a primary trait.

Based on these results, the yield can be improved if selection is made for panicle length, panicle weight, and grains panicle $^{-1}$.

Total correlations between characters in control and irradiated progenies in the M_2 generation.^a

Characters	Yield plant $^{-1}$	1,000-grain weight	Grains panicle $^{-1}$	Panicle weight	Panicle length	Panicle plant $^{-1}$
<i>Control</i>						
Height	0.311	-0.228	0.142	0.119	-0.126	0.291
Panicles plant $^{-1}$	0.699*	-0.828**	0.209	0.155	0.355	
Panicle length	0.624*	-0.145	0.789**	0.754**		
Panicle weight	0.685*	-0.005	0.991***			
Grains panicle $^{-1}$	0.703**	-0.005				
1,000-grain weight	0.532*					
<i>15 Krad</i>						
Height	0.222	0.269	-0.751**	-0.654*	-0.480	0.367
Panicles plant $^{-1}$	0.675*	0.042	-0.289	0.378	-0.618*	
Panicle length	0.778**	0.100	0.767**	0.836**		
Panicle weight	0.847**	-0.167	0.971***			
Grains panicle $^{-1}$	0.850**	-0.314				
1,000-grain weight	0.166					
<i>25 Krad</i>						
Height	-0.045	0.017	-0.683*	-0.622*	-0.039	-0.221
Panicles plant $^{-1}$	0.609*	-0.053	0.455	0.458	0.191	
Panicle length	0.896**	-0.354	0.605*	0.629		
Panicle weight	0.812**	-0.572*	0.992***			
Grains panicle $^{-1}$	0.800**	-0.608*				
1,000-grain weight	0.360					
<i>35 Krad</i>						
Height	0.434	-0.208	-0.625*	-0.660*	0.061	-0.300
Panicles plant $^{-1}$	0.626*	0.487	0.228	0.218	0.057	
Panicle length	0.804**	0.675*	0.497	0.683*		
Panicle weight	0.809**	0.643*	0.966***			
Grains panicle $^{-1}$	0.849**	0.528*				
1,000-grain weight	0.518*					

^a* and ** = significant at the 0.05 and 0.01% level, respectively.

Any change in the correlation (positive or negative) of one character with another indicates a radiation-induced effect.

Changes in the relationships observed in this study coincide with other results and might be attributed to linkage effect, gene mutation, or change polygenic systems.

For some of the character combinations, an association was nonsignificant in the

control, but significant and negative in various treatments. Such character combinations included plant height and panicle weight and plant height and grains panicle $^{-1}$ for all doses studied. The change in the direction of the correlation coefficients indicates the changes in relationships between characters. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Liangyou Peite, a new two-line hybrid rice released in China

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Two-line hybrid rice has many advantages over three-line hybrid rice. Liangyou Peite (Pei' Ai 64S/Teqing) was successfully bred over 10 yr at HRRRC. It was registered in 1994 with the Hunan Varieties Evaluation Committee and suggested for national re-

lease as one of the first two-line hybrid rice combinations. It shows high yield potential, good grain quality, and resistance to multiple diseases and insects. It had wide adaptability trials in South China and Hunan Province in 1991-93 (Tables 1 and 2).

In large-scale (3,330 ha) demonstrations in Hunan in 1991-94, Liangyou Peite yielded more than 7.5 t ha $^{-1}$ in the late season with a maximum yield of 10.4 t ha $^{-1}$. It yielded 9.0 t ha $^{-1}$ as a middle season crop, with a maximum yield of 11.3 t ha $^{-1}$. It

yielded a record of 17.1 t ha $^{-1}$ in Yongsheng County, Yunan.

Liangyou Peite had about 10% (0.8-11 t ha $^{-1}$) yield advantage over its three-line hybrid rice counterparts. Moreover, it has strong ratooning ability with an average yield of 2.3-3 t ha $^{-1}$ as a ratoon rice over the past 4 yr. In 1995, about 6,660 ha in China were planted to this hybrid.

The female parent, Pei' Ai 64 S, is the first practical thermosensitive genic male sterile line in China. It is an indica/javanica that has high combining ability and is compatible

Table 1. Performance of Liangyou Peite in South China and Hunan provincial and regional trials.

Character	South China		Hunan	
	1991	1992	1992	1993
	Mid 23 sites, 10 provinces	Late 12 sites, 8 provinces	Mid 7 sites	Mid 6 sites
Growth duration (d)	143.0	125.9	136.7	135.8
Growth duration (d) over check	-1.5	-3.4	-3.0	-5.5
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	6.2 ^a	6.7	9.5	7.7
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹) over check	1.6 ^b	8.9 ^c	4.7 ^{bd}	5.8 ^b
Basic tillers (no. m ⁻²)	99.0	-	145.5	136.5
Maximum tillers (no. m ⁻²)	478.5	-	559.5	603.0
Productive panicles (no. m ⁻²)	288	317	333	333
Spikelets (no. panicle ⁻¹)	157.8	132.6	140.1	144.5
Filled grains (no. panicle ⁻¹)	118.6	100.8	126.2	122.3
Seed set (%)	75.2	76.0	87.9	84.6
1,000-grain weight (g)	22.8	23.1	23.4	22.3
Plant height (cm)	101	93	98	106

^aBrown rice yield. ^bCheck is Shanyou 63 (three-line rice hybrid). ^cCheck is Shanyou Gui 99 (three-line rice hybrid).
^dSignificant at the 1% level.

Table 2. Grain quality of Liangyou Peite.

Grain length (mm)	5.28
Grain width (mm)	2.35
Length-width ratio	2.30
Chalky grain (%)	80.0
Chalky area (%)	5.3
Brown rice (%)	83.8
Milled rice (%)	75.9
Head rice (%)	60.0
Gelatinization temperature (°C)	4.8
Gel consistency (mm)	30
Amylose content (%)	22.4
Protein content (%)	10.3
Eating quality	Good
Remark on quality	Fine

for making indica and japonica hybrid rices. The male parent Teqing is a high-yielding inbred indica variety.

The seed yield of Pei' Ai 64 S averaged more than 3.0 t ha⁻¹ with a maximum of 5.5 t ha⁻¹. F₁ hybrid seed yield was 2.3-3.0 t ha⁻¹ in Hunan in 1995. ■

Khushboo, a quality rice cultivar for Rajasthan

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BK-805-36, a cross derived from Baran Basmati/Pusa 150, has been released as Khushboo in Rajasthan, India. It was identified in the F₆ generation at ARS, Kota.

Khushboo is a semidwarf cultivar that matures in 118-123 d when transplanted. It is suitable for either normal or late sowing and possesses ideal plant type with upright leaves, compact tillering, late leafsenescence, and horizontal flag leaf position. Panicles are long (28 cm), compact, and fully exerted. Spikelets are partially awned and straw colored. Kernels are 7.5 mm with a length-breadth ratio of 4.7.

Table 1. Performance of Khushboo in varietal trials. Kota, Rajasthan, India. 1986-91.

Year	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		CD (0.05)
	Khushboo	Basmati 370 (check)	
1986	3.4	2.6	0.4
1987	3.5	2.8	0.5
1988	2.9	2.1	0.3
1989	2.7	2.3	0.5
1990	3.5	3.0	0.3
1991	4.0	3.4	0.4
Average	3.3	2.7	
Percent over Basmati 370	23.9		

Kernel length after cooking is 13.4 mm with an elongation ratio of 1.8. The grains are long and slender, white, translucent, and strongly scented. Cooked rice is soft and well separated.

In trials conducted at Kota from 1986 to 1991, Khushboo yielded consistently higher than Basmati 370 (Table 1). In coordinated trials conducted during 1989 at 11 locations and in 1990 at 7 locations, Khushboo yielded 14.7 and 9.17% more than Basmati 370, respectively. In on-farm demonstrations conducted, Khushboo yielded 41% in 1991 and 54% higher than Basmati 370 (Table 2).

The cultivar is resistant to leaf blast and sheath rot, and moderately resistant to neck blast, brown spot, and white-backed plantopper. ■

Table 2. Khushboo grain yield in on-farm demonstrations. Kota, Rajasthan, India. 1991-92.

Year	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	Khushboo	Basmati 370 (check)
1991 (4 locations)	4.9	3.5
Percent over Basmati 370	41	
1992 (7 locations)	3.9	2.5
Percent over Basmati 370	54	

Bright-pearl 1, a fast grain-filling japonica rice

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All of the traditional late-japonica rice cultivars grown in the Yangtze River area of China require 45-50 d from heading to ripening. Sometimes the grain-filling period is longer because of unfavorable weather, resulting in low rice yield and delayed sowing of the next crop. Local farmers normally choose early-ripening rice cultivars. But the plants usually have insufficient growing time.

With a longer vegetative stage and a fast grain-filling rate, the late-japonica rice can be harvested in late October instead of early November, thus avoiding inclement weather and reducing moldy or sprouted seed. Using a fast grain-filling cultivar can increase rice quality. The ability to supply the market early means a better price for growers.

Bright-pearl 1, derived from Bin 8103/713 in 1992, is a fast grain-filling japonica rice. Its grain filling is 10-15 d faster than that of check Xiushui 11. Bin 8103 is an early ripening/japonica cultivar resistant to brown planthopper (BPH) and blast. 713 is